

**DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND
PRIVATE BUSINESS ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: In 2017, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the gross domestic product was 53.3 percent or 119,301 billion soums. (In Japan - 55%, in Germany - 54%, in the USA - 52%, in Kazakhstan - 25.6%, in Russia - 20%). 78.3 percent of the employed population in the country are engaged in small business, while in 2000 this figure was 49.7 percent.

Keywords: small business, trade, private entrepreneurship.

The share of small business in the production of industrial products was 12.9% in 2000, while in 2017 this figure was 39.6%, in agriculture - 99%, in the construction sector - 65.1%, in retail trade turnover - 88.4%. The share of small business in the total export of the country was 27%, in import - 50%, and in investment - 32%.

According to the current legislation, the annual average number of employees in agriculture, forestry and fisheries - up to 50 people, depending on the type of activity in industry - from 100 to 270 people; in the field of trade and service - subjects with 25 to 50 employees are classified as small enterprises.

The following conditions have been created for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our republic:

1. Registration time of small business entities is 30 minutes. Only one document is required for registration as an individual entrepreneur, and two documents are required for registration of a small enterprise as a legal entity.

2. The single tax payment rate, which is an important factor in creating favorable conditions for the development of small businesses in almost all sectors, is 5% of the volume of goods and services sold. In addition, the current rate of the single social payment for small business entities is 15%.

3. Newly established production enterprises with participation of foreign investment are given the right to apply the rate of taxes and compulsory payments on the day of their registration for five years. Starting from 2018, it was established that small enterprises with a land area of more than 1 hectare will pay a single land tax.

4. Financial support of small businesses is implemented in the following ways: granting loans by banks at preferential rates; guarantee in the amount of 50% of the loan funds granted to business activities of the State Fund for Entrepreneurship Support and cover the interest costs calculated on loans from commercial banks*.

5. Business interests are protected by the institution responsible for protecting the rights and legal interests of business entities. In Uzbekistan, the unscheduled inspection of the activities of small business entities has been canceled, and business entities for the first financial and economic offense have been exempted from all types of administrative fines**.

6. In all regions of the republic, entrepreneurship support centers have been established in centers operating under the principle of "one-stop shop" providing state services to business entities. "Business incubators" have been established for entities that are just starting their business activities to draw up their business plans, provide legal and practical support, as well as receive the necessary information for their activities.

7. Clusters for young entrepreneurs were organized through business training courses for entrepreneurs across the republic, implementation of projects on the basis of privatized facilities, allocation of land areas on the basis of rent at a zero rate for a period of 5 years.

As of April 1, 2018, the number of small business entities operating in the republic (excluding farmers and farms) was 238,500 (99,400 in 2001). Among them, 8.2% are small enterprises and the remaining 91.8% are micro-firms.

If we analyze this indicator by sector, we can see that 9.1 percent of small business entities operate in agriculture, 20.9 percent in industry, 11 percent in construction, 34 percent in trade and general catering, 5.2 percent in freight transportation, and 19.7 percent in other sectors.

If we look at the share of small business entities in the industry in the regions, it is 71.3% in Tashkent city, 68.4% in Namangan region, 61.3% in Jizzakh region and 55.5% in Samarkand region. The same indicator was 29.6% in Tashkent region, 23.1% in Kashkadarya region, 18.8% in Navoi region and 18% in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

At the same time, we should highlight the problems that prevent small businesses from fully realizing their potential.

1. In small business, more than 62% of employees are employed in individual businesses, while only 16% are in small enterprises and micro-firms. Low levels of employment of small enterprises correspond to Navoi (11.3%), Kashkadarya (12.4%) and Tashkent region (13.2%).

In small business, 34.2% of jobs are in agriculture, 12.7% in industry, 11.6% in construction, 13.4% in trade, and 28.1% in services.

As it can be seen from the analysis of the above points in the section of industries, we can see a relatively low position of small business in the industrial industry, where the efficiency of job creation is high compared to other industries. The preservation of this indicator at the current level of growth may cause problems related to the increase of the population's wages and real income from business activities in the future. This situation may lead to the restriction of social guarantees provided by the state to the population.

3. The share of the number of small business entities in trade remains at a high

level (26.7% of the total number of small business entities or 63.7 thousand entities). In the retail trade turnover, we can see that the share of small businesses and micro-enterprises is 20.2%, while the share of individual entrepreneurs is 69.4%, which has a negative impact on the income of the banking sector and creates inconsistencies in the taxable base of small business entities.

4. If we look at the number of small business entities in terms of regions, the largest number of entities are operating in the city of Tashkent (22.6%), Tashkent (9.6%), Fergana (8.8%) and Andijan (8.7%) regions. About 50% of the total number of small business entities operate in these four regions. It can be seen that in other regions of our republic, such as Syrdaryo (3.2%), Navoi (3.3%) and Jizzakh (4.2%), it indicates that the existing potential of small business entities is not being used sufficiently.

In the development of small business in our country, construction and finishing materials, tools and equipment, machinery spare parts and equipment, electrical engineering, chemistry, pharmaceutical products, production of many types of consumer goods, etc., are areas with high potential.

We can see the increase of the contribution of small business to the country's economy, the creation of small industrial zones, the improvement of the investment environment and the environment of competition, the expansion of the volume of public procurement within the framework of public-private partnership with small business, the strengthening of mutually beneficial cooperation between large and small enterprises, and the involvement of business entities in innovation processes.

The increasing attention to small entrepreneurship is due to its specific features:

- the ability to quickly adapt to market demand and produce quality products;
- able to meet the demand for goods and services necessary for the needs of the population in a relatively short period of time;
- the fact that the initial investment is relatively small;
- the possibility of creating new jobs soon and helping to solve the employment

problem;

- direct participation of the business owner (entrepreneur) in the implementation of activities in this regard.

The development of small business and the factors affecting it depend in many ways on the unique characteristics, advantages and disadvantages of entrepreneurship.

It is also worth noting that it is important to provide financial support to successful and promising small enterprises that have sufficient export potential, but at the same time do not have enough capital for further development.

These measures help to create more jobs in the field of effective small business, increase access to the world market, increase the export potential of the country and increase the income of the population.

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